

PURE01 data and code: User Guide

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This document outlines the data+code that generated most of the graphics in the PURE01 manuscript's main and supplementary figures.

We generated most graphics with R or Python. However, we generated **Figs. 1h, 5c, 5d, 5h, and 5i**, and **Supplementary Fig. 2g**, with GraphPad Prism v9 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, California), and, at the time of writing, Prism offers no scripting functionality.

Typically, for each panel in each figure, this document gives the name of the R script (or Python 3 Jupyter notebook), and where you will find the input data. However, please see the paragraphs below for requesting access to PURE01, ABACUS, and IMvigor010 cohort data.

Typically, locations of input data files are indicated either by 1) repository/folder_name (e.g. repository/scRNA-Seq/scRNA5/...), or, 2) for a specific figure, the figure's 'data' subfolder (e.g. for Fig_1f_Hallmarks, data/PURE01_..._Hallmarks.xlsx).

With the PURE01 publication, Supplementary Data will offer cluster (i.e. subtype) calls, clinical data, NanoString GeoMx (digital spatial profiling, DSP) protein data, and classifier predictions on ABACUS and IMvigor010 cohorts. For the RT4 cell line we supply 'bigwig' files for the UCSC hg38 genome browser.

However, following publication, many raw and some processed PURE01 data files will be available only from the PURE01 Data Access Committee (DAC) at EGAS00001005549. If you wish to access these files, please place a request with the PURE01 DAC. The manuscript gives an email address for this.

For the ABACUS n=84 pre-treatment cohort, Supplementary Table 5 reports GLMnet classifier subtype predictions. However, we are unable to supply ABACUS data; please request access to data for that cohort through its DAC (EGAS00001004445). The manuscript gives an email address for this.

Similarly, we are unable to supply any data for the IMvigor010 cohort; please request access to data for that cohort through its DAC (EGAS00001004997). The manuscript gives an email address for this.

Figure 1

Fig. 1a: consensus expression subtypes

1. Consensus expression clusters for Fig. 1a, and the blue-white consensus membership heatmap in Supp. Fig. 2a

- Script: Fig_1a_and_Supp_Fig_2a_consensus_subtypes.R
 - 1) Input: Please request PURE01_n82_19496_coding_genes_FPKMs.RData and PURE01_n113_19496_coding_genes_FPKMs.RData from the PURE01 DAC (see above, at EGAS00001005549)
- Note: the run output from ConsensusClusterPlus (CCP) for PURE01 n=82 is in data/PURE01_n82.1950_coding_FPKMs.CCP_Spearman_PAM.maxK_8.reps_10k.pltem_0.85.RData. For repeatable clustering results, please read in this .RData file.

2. The heatmap

- Script: Fig_1a_heatmap.R
- Inputs:

- 2) Please request PURE01_RNAseq_gexp_counts_n82.RData and PURE01_n113_19496_coding_genes_FPKMs.RData from the PURE01 DAC
- 3. Simple covariate track showing five PURE01 n=82 subtypes
 - Script: Figs_1a_and_5a_PURE01_n82_n113_covariate_tracks.R
 - Inputs: the R script was written to use PURE01.20210806.RData, which can be requested from the PURE01 DAC. As an alternative, please modify the R script to use the read_xl package to read the Supplementary Data shown below.
 - "master.table" = Supp Data 1
 - "subtypes.n113" = Supp Data 10
 - "n27.matched.pairs" = Supp Data 9
 - "estimate.n82" = Supp Data 7
 - "estimate.n113" = Supp Data 14
 - "mcpcounter.n82" = Supp Data 8
 - "mcpcounter.n113" = Supp Data 15
 - "abacus.predicted.subtypes" = Supp Data 5
 - "regulon.activities.n82" = Supp Data 16

Fig. 1b: Stacked barplot for PURE01 n=82 response

- Script: Fig_1b.R
- Input: Supplementary Data 1
- Fig_1b_data_README.txt: The R script was written to read an .RData file. Please modify the script to use Supplementary Data 1 instead.

Fig. 1c: Kaplan-Meier plot for PURE01 n=82, censored at 24 mo

- Script: Fig_1c.R
- Input: We do not supply event status and time data that would generate a KM plot. Please request 'PURE01_master_table_with_Path.response_and_times.RData' from the PURE01 DAC. The R script was written to use this .RData file.

Fig. 1d: PD-L1(+) barplot for PURE01 n=82 subtypes

- Script: Fig_1d.R
- Input: Please request PURE01_n82_19496_coding_genes_FPKMs.RData from the PURE01 DAC. The R script was written to use this file.

Fig. 1e: Predicted Lund, TCGA (mRNA), consensusMIBC, and MDA subtypes for PURE01 n=82

- Script: Fig_1e.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) Please request PURE01_n82_19496_coding_genes_FPKMs.RData from the PURE01 DAC. The BLCAsubtyping and consensusMIBC R packages will run on the FPKMs.
 - 2) n=82 cluster calls from Supplementary Table 1.

Fig. 1f: CERNO test results for Hallmark gene sets on PURE01 n=82 subtypes

- Script: Fig_1f_Hallmarks.R
- Input: data/PURE01_n82_5_subtypes_CERNO_tests_Hallmarks.xlsx

Fig. 1g: CERNO test results for Mariathasan gene sets (see Mariathasan_human_gene_signatures.RData_README.txt) on PURE01 n=82 subtypes

- Script: Fig_1g_Mariathasan.R
- Input: data/PURE01_n82_5_subtypes_CERNO_tests_Mariathasan.xlsx

Fig. 1h: CMap results for PURE01 n=82 subtypes

- Fig_1h_README.txt: The line graph in Fig. 1h was plotted with Graphpad Prism; we supply no script. We drew the simple blue-white heatmap by hand.
- Input: CMap results: data/Fig_1h.xlsx

Figure 2

Fig. 2a: Summary of classifier results for ABACUS n=84

- See: Fig_2a_README.txt
- Script: Fig_2a.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) Please request PURE01_n82_19496_coding_genes_FPKMs.RData from the PURE01 DAC
 - 2) Please request ABACUS RNA-Seq data from the ABACUS DAC

Fig. 2b: CERNO test results for Hallmark gene sets on predicted PURE01 subtypes in ABACUS n=84

- Script: Fig_2b.R
- Input: CERNO Hallmark test results for each predicted subtype:
data/ABACUS_n84_predicted_S1_to_S5_CERNO_tests_Hallmarks.xlsx

Fig. 2c: Kaplan-Meier plot for ABACUS DFS, censored at 24 mo.

- Script: Fig_2c_ABACUS_KM.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) Please request ABACUS.alias.id.txt from the PURE01 DAC
 - 2) Supplementary Table 5 - GLMnet classifier predictions for ABACUS n=84
 - 3) Please request ABACUS clinical data from the ABACUS DAC

Fig. 2d: PD-L1(+) grouped barplot for PURE01 and ABACUS

- Script: Figs_2d_2f_and_Supp_Fig_2e.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) For PURE01 n=82, Supplementary Data 1
 - 2) Supplementary Table 5 (GLMnet classifier predictions for ABACUS n=84)
 - 3) Please request ABACUS.alias.id.txt from the PURE01 DAC.
 - 4) Please request ABACUS RNA-Seq data from the ABACUS DAC.
(anon_abacus.RNAseq.pdata.public.csv)

Fig. 2e: For ABACUS n=84, stacked barplot of pathological response (CR/PR/NR).

- Script: Fig_2e.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) Please request ABACUS.alias.id.txt from the PURE01 DAC
 - 2) Please request ABACUS RNA-Seq and clinical data from the ABACUS DAC

Fig. 2f: Overall response (OR = CR or PR): grouped barplot for PURE01 and ABACUS

- Script: Figs_2d_2f_and_Supp_Fig_2e.R
- Inputs: as for Figure 2d

Fig. 2g: Kaplan-Meier plot for the MIBC samples in the IMvigor01 cohort's Atezo (treatment) arm.

- Script: IMvigor010_KM.R
- Inputs
 - 1) Supplementary Table 25 (GLMnet classifier predictions for the IMvigor010 cohort)
 - 2) Please request IMvigor010 metadata from the IMvigor010 DAC.
(IMvigor010.metadata.merged.csv)

Figure 3

Fig. 3a: CERNO GSEA test results for MSigDB Hallmarks, for 13 mutated genes in PURE01 n=82

- Script: Fig_3a_i_and_ii.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) Please request Fig_3a_PURE01_read_counts.csv from the PURE01 DAC
 - 2) Please request Fig_3a_PURE01_mut_data.xlsx from the PURE01 DAC
 - 3) Supplementary Data 1 gives ConsensusClusterPlus cluster calls for PURE01 n=82.
 - 4) Please download msigdb_v7.X.xml from MSigDB

Fig. 3b: Mutations in 5 genes, by responders (CR or PR) vs nonresponders

- See Fig_3b_data_README.txt
- Input: Please request Fig_3b.xlsx from the PURE01 DAC

Fig. 3c: Oncoprint of somatic mutations and somatic copy number alterations for each PURE01 n=82 subtype

- Script: Fig_3c.R
- Inputs: Please request from the PURE01 DAC -
 - 1) Fig_3c_cluster.annotations.csv
 - 2) Fig_3c_data.csv

Figure 4

Fig. 4a: ESTIMATE and MCP-counter results for PURE01 n=82 subtypes

- Script: Figs_4a_and_Supp_Fig_4a.R
- Input: Please request PURE01.20210806.RData from the PURE01 DAC; alternatively, please adjust the R script to use the Supplementary Data XLSX:
 - "master.table" = Supp Data 1
 - "subtypes.n113" = Supp Data 10
 - "n27.matched.pairs" = Supp Data 9
 - "estimate.n82" = Supp Data 7
 - "estimate.n113" = Supp Data 14
 - "mcpcounter.n82" = Supp Data 8
 - "mcpcounter.n113" = Supp Data 15
 - "abacus.predicted.subtypes" = Supp Data 5
 - "regulon.activities.n82" = Supp Data 16

Fig. 4b: Schematic diagram of the NanoString GeoMx DSP workflow.

- No scripts
- Inputs: none.
- Comment: we generated the table of the number of proteins in each probe group with data in Supplementary Data 20.

Fig. 4c: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) results for SNR-normalized DSP data for TME AOIs for S1, S2, and S4

- Script: Figs_4c_and_4d.R
- Input: Supplementary Data 21 (SNR-normalized DSP protein levels)

Fig. 4d: Heatmap of DSP abundance for 13 TME proteins in S1, S2, S4

- Script: Figs_4c_and_4d.R
- Input: Supplementary Data 21 (SNR-normalized DSP protein levels)

Figure 5

Fig. 5a: There are two Sankey-like bezier-curve plots: i) n=82 pre-treatment PURE01 samples. ii) 27 matched pre-post-treatment PURE01 samples.

- Comments: Each bezier curve shows the locations of one PURE01 tumor sample in two CCP clustering solutions. The n=113 clustering result in (ii) also has a grey-black pre-post-treatment covariate track.
- Script: Fig_5a_bezier.R.
- Input: CCP cluster calls for PURE01 n=82 (Supplementary Data 1) and n=113 (Supplementary Data 10)
- Covariate tracks: Figs_1a_5a_PURE01_n82_n113_covariate_tracks.R

Fig. 5b: Micrographs of representative samples from S6 and S7

- The figure shows representative micrographs, so we supply no scripts, and there are no input data files.

Fig. 5c: Samples that were N0/N1 in PURE01 n=113 subtypes S6 and S7

- Script: Plotted with Graphpad Prism; we supply no script.
- Inputs: see Figs_5c_5d_README.txt

Fig. 5d: Violin plots of Tumor Area for PURE01 n=113 subtypes S6 and S7

- Script: Plotted with Graphpad Prism; we supply no script.
- Inputs: Supplementary Data 13

Fig. 5e: CERNO test results for Hallmarks for PURE01 n=82 consensus subtypes, and for n=113 subtypes S6 and S7 (see Fig. 5a).

- Script: Fig_5e_Hallmarks.R
- Input: Supplementary Data 12
- Note: In Fig. 5e, we manually added the Hallmark GSEA dot diagram for PURE01 n=82 from Fig. 1f.

Fig. 5f: CERNO tests for Mariathasan gene sets for PURE01 n=113 subtypes S6 and S7

- Script: Fig_5f_Mariathasan.R
- Input: data/PURE01_n113_S6_S7_CERNO_tests_Mariathasan.xlsx
- Note: In Fig. 5f, we manually added Fig. 1g's Mariathasan GSEA dot diagram for PURE01 n=82.

Fig. 5g: ESTIMATE deconvolution pre-vs-post for n=27 matched pre-post-treatment sample pairs

- Script: Fig_5g_compare_ESTIMATE_pre_vs_post.R
- Inputs: Supplementary Data 1, 7, 9, and 10

Fig. 5h: CMap results for PURE01 n=113 subtype S6

- Script: Plotted with Graphpad Prism; we supply no script. See: Fig_5h_5i_README.txt
- Input: data/Fig_5h_and_5i.xlsx

Fig. 5i: CMap results for PURE01 n=113 subtype S7

- Script: Plotted with Graphpad Prism; we supply no script. See: Fig_5h_5i_README.txt
- Input: data/Fig_5h_and_5i.xlsx

Figure 6

Fig 6a: KDM5B regulon target genes

- Script: Fig_6a.R
- Input: data/Fig_6a_igraph_KDM5B.RData (2.4 KB)

Fig 6b: Validation of the negative relationship between KDM5B regulon activity and ImmuneScore in PURE01 and TCGA-BLCA.

- For PURE01 n=82
 - Script: validate_KDM5B_PURE01.R
 - Inputs: Supplementary Data 7, 15, and 16
- For TCGA n=404
 - Script: validate_KDM5B_TCGA_BLCA.R
 - Input: From the TCGA BLCA 2018 publication's 'master table', we have precalculated: data/TCGA_BLCA.merged.KDM5B.estimate.txt

Fig 6c: scRNA-Seq clusters: assigning cell types, re-clustering epithelial cells, and annotating with a luminal signature score, KDM5B expression, and KDM5B(+) and KDM5B(-) regulon AUCs.

- Python 3 Jupyter notebook: scRNAseq_Analysis_code.ipynb
 - The Python code has all the information needed to run the script and generate the manuscript's scRNA-Seq figure panels.
- Inputs: please request scRNA-Seq data from the PURE01 DAC:
 - Folders: scRNA5, scRNA6, scRNA7
 - Each folder contains three files: barcodes.tsv.gz, features.tsv.gz, matrix.mtx.gz
 - Total file size: 157 MB

Fig 6d: Volcano plots for RT4 cells treated with the KDM5Bi C70 vs. DMSO (control), and with the FGFRi erdafitinib vs DMSO.

- Script: Fig_6d.R
- Inputs: please request from the PURE01 DAC -
 - 1) Fig 6d_C70vDMSO.htseq.edgeR.txt
 - 2) Fig 6d_FGFRivsDMSO.htseq.edgeR.txt

Fig 6e: CERNO GSEA test results for Hallmarks for RT4 cells, for C70 vs DMSO and FGFRi vs DMSO. Dot areas are proportional to AUCs.

- Script: Fig_6e.R
- Inputs: CERNO test results
 - 1) data/Fig6e_C70_vs_DMSO_C70_up.csv (each data file is ~3-5 kB)
 - 2) data/Fig6e_C70_vs_DMSO_DMSO_up.csv
 - 3) data/Fig6e_FGFRi_vs_DMSO_DMSO_up.csv
 - 4) data/Fig6e_FGFRi_vs_DMSO_FGFRi_up.csv

Fig 6f: Chromatin accessibility profiles from bulk ATAC-seq data for RT4 cells treated with the KDM5Bi C70 or with DMSO control.

- Script: Figure 6f was generated using deepTools, which was run via a Unix bash script (see Methods: ATAC-seq).
- Inputs: see Methods: ATAC-seq.

Fig 6g: ATAC-seq and RNA-seq read pileup profiles in RT4 cells, for C70 treatment and DMSO control

- Script: We supply no script.
- Inputs: GRCh38/hg38 'bigwig' files can be displayed in the UCSC hg38 genome browser.
 - 1) data/RT4_C70_ATACseq.bw (97MB)
 - 2) data/RT4_C70_RNAseq.bw (72MB)
 - 3) data/RT4_DMSO_ATACseq.bw (123 MB)
 - 4) data/RT4_DMSO_RNAseq.bw (70 MB)

Figure 7. Summary characteristics of PURE-01 consensus expression subtypes.

Radarcharts for CERNO tests on Mariathasan gene sets

- Script: Fig_7_Mariathasan_radarcharts.R
- Inputs: from Fig. 1g: /data/ PURE01_n82_5_subtypes_CERNO_tests_Mariathasan.xlsx

Pie charts for PD-L1+/-

- Script: Fig_7_PDL1_piecharts.R
- Inputs: Supplementary Table 1

Pie charts for CR/PR/NR response

- Script: Fig_7_response_piecharts.R
- Inputs: Supplementary Table 1

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Enriched and repressed gene sets for CR vs NR samples in the PURE01 cohort.

- See: Supp_Fig_1_README.txt
- Inputs
 - 1) data/human_gene_signatures.RData
 - 2) data/pure01.FPKMs.keep.ordered.means_and_medians.ordered_by_StoN_DESC.CR_vs_NR.txt
 - 3) data/tmod_CR_vs_NR.20211201.xlsx

Supplementary Figure 2. Consensus clustering of n=82 and n=113 cohorts; relationship of PD-L1(+) to OR; representative micrographs of n=82 subtypes.

Comments for **Supp Fig. 2a-d**: when you run ConsensusClusteringPlus (CCP) from the R script, CCP will write out a PDF. The PDF will include blue-white consensus membership heatmaps for the range of clustering solutions you have requested (e.g. you may have requested clustering solutions that range from 2 clusters to 8 clusters). The PDF will also include a 'CDF' plot, a 'delta' plot, and a 'tracking' plot. Please run CCP on either the n=82 or n=113 FPKM data. There is a potentially awkward issue: the numbers (i.e. 'names') that CCP assigns to clusters i.e. subtypes may change between CCP runs, even when you set a random seed. See Supp_Fig_2a_to_2d_README.txt. However, so that you can work with the CCP output that we used, we supply the RData run output from CCP for PURE01 n=82 – in the data subfolder for Fig. 1a -

PURE01_n82.1950_coding_FPKMs.CCP_Spearman_PAM.maxK_8.reps_10k.pltem_0.85.RData

Supp. Fig. 2a: ConsensusClusterPlus (CCP) Consensus membership heatmap for five clusters for PURE01 n=82 or n=113.

- Script: Figs_1a_and_Supp_Fig_2a_consensus_subtypes.R - in the Fig_1a folder
- Inputs: Please request the following files from the PURE01 DAC:
 - 1) PURE01_n82_19496_coding_genes_FPKMs.RData
 - 2) PURE01_n113_19496_coding_genes_FPKMs.RData

Supp. Fig. 2b: Cumulative (empirical) distribution function (CDF) graph for clustering solutions with between 2 and 8 clusters, for the PURE01 n=82 cohort. This is an output from CCP. We manually highlighted the five-cluster solution.

Supp. Fig. 2c: Consensus membership heatmap for seven clusters for PURE01 pre+post-treatment n=113. This is an output from CCP.

Supp. Fig. 2d: CDF graph for clustering solutions with between 2 and 8 clusters, for the PURE01 n=113 cohort. We manually highlighted the seven-cluster solution. This is an output from CCP.

Supp. Fig. 2e: Across PURE01 n=82 subtypes, the fraction of PD-L1(+) samples and the fraction of OR=CR+PR samples.

- See: Supp_Fig_2e_README.txt

Supp. Fig. 2f: Representative H&E micrographs for each PURE01 subtype. Scalebars are 100 μ m.

- See: Fig_S2f_README.txt

Supp. Fig. 2g: CMap results for predicted PURE01 subtypes in the ABACUS n=84 cohort

- See: Fig_2c_README.txt
- Script: Curves were plotted with Graphpad Prism; we supply no script. We drew the simple heatmap by hand.
- Input: ABACUS CMap results are in data/Supp_Fig_2g_data.xlsx

Supp. Fig. 2h: Kaplan-Meier plot for MIBC samples in the IMvigor010 cohort's 'observational' arm.

- See Supp_Fig_2h_README.txt. Supplementary Table 25 gives the classifier subtype predictions on the IMvigor010 cohort. Please request the IMvigor010 metadata from the IMvigor010 DAC.

Supplementary Figure 3. Classifier parameter tuning and accuracy.

- See Supp_Fig_3_README.txt - While we supply no R scripts for this figure, we provide the classifier, with how-to-use instructions, at <https://github.com/csgroen/mibcCPIclass>.

Supplementary Figure 4. Comparing CMap results for PURE01 subtypes and predicted ABACUS subtypes. For each comparison, we give a Spearman correlation coefficient and its p-value; correlations reported are between connectivity scores for genetic perturbations in the CMap v1.0 dataset. A positive score indicates that the CMap expression signature for a genetic perturbation (e.g. IFNG OE) was positively correlated with the subtype-specific PURE01 and ABACUS signature inputs. Kd = knockdown, oe = overexpression.

- Script: As the graphics in this figure were plotted with GraphPad Prism, we supply no script.
- Inputs: data/Supp_Fig_4_data.xlsx (this XLSX file gives CMap results for each PURE01 n=82 subtype and classifier-predicted subtype in ABACUS n=84)

Supplementary Figure 5. Somatic mutations and copy number alterations in PURE01, ABACUS, and TCGA-BLCA cohorts. Alterations in FGFR3, KRAS, and PPARG in PURE01 S1. Distributions of PURE01 TMB by subtype and response.

Supp. Fig. 5a: Somatic mutations and copy number alterations in PURE01, ABACUS, and TCGA-BLCA cohorts.

Supp. Fig. 5b: Alterations in FGFR3, KRAS, and PPARG in PURE01 S1

Supp. Fig. 5c,d: Distributions of PURE01 TMB by subtype and response

- Inputs:
 - 1) Supplementary Data 1 (PURE01 'master table')

- 2) Please request 'PURE01_All_data_separated.csv' from the PURE01 DAC.
- 3) Please use the public somatic mutation data in the 2018 TCGA BLCA publication's (PMID: 30096301) 'master table'.
- 4) Please request 'PURE01 TMB_by_Cluster.csv' from the PURE01 DAC.
- 5) Please request ABACUS mutation data from the ABACUS DAC.

Supplementary Figure 6

Supp. Fig. 6a: FGFR3 somatic mutations and CCND1 somatic copy number amplifications were enriched in subtype S1 in PURE01 n=82 and in predicted S1 in ABACUS n=84 cohorts. The Supp_Figs_6a_6b folder contains two R scripts: Supp_Fig_6a.R and Supp_Fig_6b.R.

- Script: Supp_Figs_6a_6b/Supp_Fig_6a.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) Supplementary Data 5 (ABACUS n=84 GLM classifier-predicted PURE01 subtypes).
 - 2) Please request 'ABACUS.alias.id.txt' from the PURE01 DAC.
 - 3) Please request 'mutation data PURE01_All_data_separated.csv' from the PURE01 DAC.
 - 4) Please request ABACUS mutation data from the ABACUS DAC.

Supp. Fig. 6b: Per-subtype oncoprints for predicted subtypes in the ABACUS n=84 pre-treatment cohort.

- Script: Supp_Figs_6a_6b/Supp_Fig_6b.R
- Inputs: Please request ABACUS somatic mutation data from the ABACUS DAC.

Supplementary Figure 7. Distributions of ESTIMATE and MCP-counter deconvolution results and DSP protein data.

Supp. Fig. 7a-c: Per-subtype distributions of ESTIMATE's StromalScore and ImmuneScore.

- See: Supp_Fig_7_README.txt
- R script: Supp_Fig_7a_to_7c_compare_ESTIMATE_MCPcounter_and_DSP_proteins.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) Supplementary Data 7 (ESTIMATE results for PURE01 n=82 clusters)
 - 2) Supplementary Data 8 (MCP-counter results for PURE01 n=82 clusters)
 - 3) Supplementary Data 21 (SNR-normalized DSP protein levels)

Supp. Fig. 7d: Distributions of SNR-normalized DSP protein data for CR vs NR samples across subtypes.

- Script: Supp_Fig_7d_ImmuneScore_CR_vs_NR.R
- Input: Supplementary Data 7 (ESTIMATE results for PURE01 n=82 clusters)

Supplementary Figure 8. Extended analysis of DSP TME proteins in PURE01 subtypes S1, S2, and S4.

- Script: Supp_Fig_8.R
Note: this script handles the correlation heatmaps (Supp. Fig. 8c and 8d), but does not handle the heatmaps in Supp. Fig. 8e and 8f.
- Inputs
 - 1) Supplementary Data 20 (Probe groups for DSP proteins)
 - 2) Supplementary Data 21 (DSP protein levels, normalized by Signal-to-noise Ratio (SNR))

Supp. Fig. 8a,b: Thresholding DSP proteins in TME AOs for S1, S2, and S4, using negative controls.

a) For 17 NR AOs (see Supp_Fig_8.R)

b) For 21 CR AOs (see Supp_Fig_8.R)

Supp. Fig. 8c,d: Correlation heatmaps for the 35 NR proteins and 42 CR proteins in **Supp. Figs. 8a,b**.

Supp. Fig. 8e,f: Yes/no heatmaps of functional probe groups for proteins in correlation heatmaps. Probe groups with no proteins in a heatmap are shaded pale grey. Rectangles and triangles, added manually, highlight certain parts of the correlation heatmaps. Note that Supp_Fig_8.R script does not include these heatmaps.

Supplementary Figure 9. Immune cell types by deconvolution of bulk RNA-seq data; BCR gene usage.

Supp. Fig. 9a: MCP-counter deconvolution of immune cell types for the five consensus subtypes in the PURE01 n=82 pre-treatment cohort, and the seven consensus subtypes in the PURE01 n=113 pre- and post-treatment cohort.

- See Supp_Fig_9a_README.txt: Please use Fig_4a_and_Supp_Fig_9a.R, in the Fig_4/Fig_4a_heatmaps folder.
- Please modify the R script (add package 'readxl') to use Supplementary Data 7, 14, 8 and 15 (estimate.n82, estimate.n113, mcpcounter.n82, and mcpcounter.n113)

Supp. Fig. 9b: Distributions of FPKMs for ten marker genes for cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs) in PURE01 subtypes. The table at the right compares distributions of CAF FPKMs between S5 and S3.

- Script: PURE01_subtypes_CAFs.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) Supplementary Table 1 ('master table')
 - 2) Please request from the PURE01 DAC: 'PURE01_n82_19496_coding_genes_FPKMs.RData' and 'PURE01_master_table_with_Path.response_and_times.RData'.

Supp. Fig. 9c: Comparing distributions of ESTIMATE outputs for S6 and S7.

- Script: Supp_Fig_9c_estimate_S6_S7.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) Supplementary Data 10 (consensus clustering results for PURE01 n=113)
 - 2) Please request 'PURE01_n113_19496_coding_genes_FPKMs.RData' from the PURE01 DAC

Supp. Fig 9d: IGHJ1 gene usage as a function of PURE01 subtype, and for ORR (CR|PR) vs NR.
and

Supp. Fig. 9e: For IGHJ1, relationship between a subtype's mean gene usage frequency and the fraction of CR in (CR+NR) samples. The inset table gives the number of CR, NR, and total samples in each subtype after IGH clonotype filtering.

- Script: Supp_Figs_9d_9e_immunarch.R
- Input: Please request 'PURE01_n82_TRUST4_immdata.RData' from the PURE01 DAC.

Supplementary Figure 10. Micrographs of representative H&E-stained post-therapy tumors from n=113 clusters 6 and 7. Heavy black lines are explained in Methods. Scalebars are 4 mm.

- Supp_Fig_10_README.txt: Supp. Fig. 10 shows micrographs. There are no scripts and no input data.

Supplementary Figure 11. The KDM5B regulon in PURE01 n=82. scRNA-Seq marker genes. KDM5i and FGFRi treatments.

Supp. Fig. 11a: Regulon activity heatmap across the five PURE01 n=82 subtypes, for the 25 RTN-identified regulons that were present in the 720 EpiFactors chromatin regulators. Text to the right gives the EpiFactors DB function of each gene.

- Script: Supp_Fig_11a_11b.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) data/epifactors.genes.csv (PMID: 36350659)
 - 2) Supplementary Data 15 (MCP-counter results for PURE01 n=113 clusters)

Supp. Fig. 11b: Distributions of ESTIMATE ImmuneScore (left, bottom), KDM5B and FGFR3 RNA-Seq expression (FPKM, above, centre and right), and KDM5B regulon activity (centre, below) across the five PURE01 n=82 subtypes.

- See Supp_Fig_11b_README.txt

Supp. Fig. 11c: Statistical significance of the top five Reactome pathways for the STRING-inferred interactome for KDM5B negative target genes.

- Script: Supp_Fig_11c.R
- Inputs:
 - 1) data/enrichment.RCTM_string_neg_targets.tsv
 - 2) data/KDM5B_neg_tgt_genes.txt

Supp. Fig. 11d: Marker genes for reclustered epithelial cell clusters.

- Supp_Fig_11d_README.txt
 - See Methods.
 - Please request raw scRNA-seq FASTQ files from the PURE01 DAC.
 - See Fig. 6b's Python 3 script: scRNAseq_Analysis_code.ipynb."

Supp. Fig. 11e: Venn diagram for RT4 cells comparing differentially expressed genes after treatment with the KDM5B inhibitor C70 or the FGFR inhibitor Erdafitinib.

- Please request from the PURE01 DAC -
 - C70vDMSO.htseq.edgeR.txt
 - FGFRivsDMSO.htseq.edgeR.txt

Supp. Figs. 11f,g: Top enriched and repressed MSigDB Hallmark gene sets from CERNO GSEA tests in RT4 cells treated with **f)** the KDM5i C70, and **g)** the FGFRi erdafitinib.

Script: Supp_Figs_11f_and_11g.R

Inputs: please request from the PURE01 DAC -

- 1) C70_htseq.fpkms.txt
- 2) FGFRi_htseq.fpkms.txt